

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
FLOUXETINE, OLANZAPINE AND OLANZAPINE IN BULK
AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS**

Rasheeda Amreen *and Dr.Iffath Rizwana

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis &QA, Deccan School of Pharmacy, Hyderabad- 500001

Abstract:

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine by using Zodiac sil C18 column (4.6×150mm)5μ, flow rate was 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio was (70:30 v/v) methanol: phosphate buffer(KH₂PO₄and K₂HPO₄) phosphate pH 3 (pH was adjusted with orthophosphoric acid),detection wavelength was 240nm. The instrument used was WATERS HPLC Auto Sampler, Separation module 2695, photo diode array detector 996, Empower-software version-2. The retention times were found to be 2.170 mins and 7.025 mins. The % purity of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine was found to be 99.1% and 98.2% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Fluoxetine and Olanzapine such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 12294, 1.27 and 10491 and 1.03, the resolution was found to be 8.67. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine was found in concentration range of 16μg-80μg and 25μg-125μg and correlation coefficient (r²) was found to be 0.999 and 0.998, % recovery was found to be 101.7% and 102.0%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.8and 0.5, % RSD for intermediate precision was 1.99 and 1.82 respectively. The precision study was precision, robustness and repeatability.LOD value was 2.17 and 0.0372 and LOQ value was 6.60 and 0.1125 respectively.Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Fluoxetine and Olanzapine in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

Keywords: Zodiac sil C18 column, Fluoxetine and Olanzapine, RP-HPLC

*** Corresponding author:**

Rasheeda Amreen *

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis &QA,

Deccan School of Pharmacy,

Hyderabad- 500001

QR code

Please cite this article in press Rasheeda Amreen and Iffath Rizwana., **RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Fluoxetine, Olanzapine and Olanzapine in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(09).

INTRODUCTION:**1.1 DEFINITIONS**

- **Analytical chemistry** is the study of the separation, identification, and quantification of the chemical components of natural and artificial materials. It deals with methods for determining the chemical composition of samples of matter.
- A **Qualitative Method** yields information about the identity of atomic or molecular species or the functional groups in the sample.
- A **Quantitative Method**, in contrast, provides numerical information as to the relative amount of one or more of these components [1,2].
- **Pharmaceutical analysis** may be defined as a process or a sequence of processes to identify

and/or quantify a substance or drug, the components of a pharmaceutical solution or mixture or the determination of the structures of chemical compounds used in the formulation of pharmaceutical product [2].

- **Analytical procedure** refers to the way of performing the analysis. It should describe in detail the steps necessary to perform each analytical test. This may include but is not limited to: the sample, the reference standard and the reagents preparations, use of the apparatus, generation of the calibration curve, use of the formulae for the calculation, etc [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Chemicals and standards used****List of chemicals and standards used**

S.No	Chemicals	Manufacturer Name	Grade
1.	Water	Merck	HPLC grade
2.	Methanol	Merck	HPLC grade
3.	Acetonitrile	Merck	HPLC grade
4.	Ortho phosphoric acid	Merck	G.R
5.	KH ₂ PO ₄	Merck	G.R
6.	K ₂ HPO ₄	Merck	G.R
7.	0.22μ Nylon filter	Advanced lab	HPLC grade
8.	0.45μ filter paper	Millipore	HPLC grade
9.	Flouxatine and Olanzapine	In – House	In- House

➤ **2 Instruments used****List of instruments used**

S.No	Instrument name	Model number	Soft ware	Manufacturers Name
1	HPLC-auto sampler –UV detector	Separation module2695, UV.detector2487	Empower-software version-2	Waters
2	U.V double beam spectrometer	UV 3000+	U.V win soft ware	Lab India
3	Digital weighing balance(sensitivity 5mg)	ER 200A	-	Ascotet
4	pH meter	AD 102U	-	ADWA

Method development for the simultaneous estimation of Flouxatine and Olanzapine by using RP-HPLC.

1. Selection of mobile phase
2. Selection of detection wavelength
3. Selection of column
4. Selection of solvent delivery system
5. Selection of flow rate
6. Selection of column temperature
7. Selection of diluent

8. Selection of test concentration and injection volume

1. Selection of mobile phase

- pH 3 phosphate buffer : Methanol (70 : 30% v/v)
- Buffer pH should be between 2 to 8.
- Below 2: siloxane linkages are cleaved. Above 8: dissolution of silica.
- pH selected: 3 ±0.05

- pH controls the elution properties by controlling the ionization characteristics.
- Reasons: To decrease the retention and improve separation. Good Response, Area, Tailing factor, Resolution.

2. Selection of wavelength: 10 mg of Flouxatine and Olanzapine was dissolved in mobile phase. The solution was scanned from 200-400 nm the spectrum was obtained. The overlay spectrum was used for selection of wavelength for Flouxatine and Olanzapine. The isobestic point was taken as detection wavelength.

Selection of column

- Heart of HPLC made of 316 grade stainless steel packed with stationary phase.

Silica based columns with different cross linking's in the increasing order of polarity are as follows:

←----- Non-polar-----moderately polar-----
---Polar-----→

C₁₈< C₈< C₆< Phenyl < Amino <Cyano<
Silica

- In reverse phase chromatography, hydrophobic interaction between drug molecule and the alkyl chains on the column packing material.
- Column is selected based on solubility, polarity and chemical differences among analysts and Column selected: i.e. Symmetry C18 column (4.6 x150 mm) 5 μ.

4. Selection of solvent delivery system

- Always preferable solvent delivery system.
- More chance of getting reproducible result on retention time of analytes.
- More economic than gradient technique.

5. Selection of flow rate

Acceptable limit: - Not more than 2.5 ml/min

- Flow rate selected was 1ml/min
- Flow rate is selected based on

Reasons:

- ❖ For earlier elution of analyte and elution of all impurities within 6.0 min.
- ❖ Information from the reference method in literature.

6. Selection of diluent

- Selection of diluent is based on the solubility of the analyte
- Diluent selected: Methanol : phosphate buffer pH 3 (70 : 30v/v)

7 Selection of column temperature:

- Preferable temperature is ambient or room temperature.

Reasons:

- ❖ To elute all impurities along with analyte with in 10.0 min of run time.
- ❖ Less retention time
- ❖ Good peak shape
- ❖ Higher theoretical plates.
- ❖ Good resolution.

Selection of test concentration and injection volume

Test concentration is finalized after it is proved that API is completely extractable at the selected test concentration.

- Test concentration is fixed based upon the response of API peak at selected detector wavelength.
- Flouxatine and Olanzapine label claimed 8 mg and 12.5 mg.
- And the test concentration selected is 10 ppm.
- Injection volume selected was 10μL.

Reason: good peak area, retention time, peak symmetry.

(Optimised method):

Chromatographic conditions

Column	: Zodiac sil C18 column (4.6×150mm)5μ
Mobile phase ratio	: Methanol: pH 3 phosphate buffer (70: 30 % v/v)
Detection wavelength	: 240 nm
Flow rate	: 1.0ml/min
Injection volume	: 20μl
Column temperature	: Ambient
Auto sampler temperature	: Ambient
Run time	: 10min
Retention time	: 2.170 and 7.280 mins

Details of Trial

S.No	Peak name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Flouxatine	2.170	8821623	340253	533	1.12	1.3
2	Olanzapine le	7.280	2854632	167348	2631	1.21	1.41

Observation

The separation was good, peak shape was good, so we conclude that there is no required for reduce the retention times of peaks, so it is taken as final method.

Procedure

Preparation of phosphate buffer

2.95 grams of KH_2PO_4 and 5.45 grams of K_2HPO_4 was weighed and taken into a 1000ml beaker, dissolved and diluted to 1000ml with HPLC water and pH was adjusted to 3 with ortho phosphoric acid. The resulting solution was sonicated and filtered.

Preparation of mobile phase

Mix a mixture of above buffer 300 ml (30%) and 700 ml of methanol (HPLC grade-70%) and degassed in ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes. Filter through 0.22 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluents preparation

Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Preparation of the Flouxatine and Olanzapine standard and sample solution

Sample solution preparation:

Accurately weigh and transfer 59.8 mg of Olanzapine and Flouxatine Tablet powder into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume

up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution).

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine & Flouxatine the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Standard solution preparation

Accurately weigh and transfer 12.5 mg & 8 mg of Olanzapine and Flouxatine working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonic ate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine & Flouxatine the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure

10 μ L of the blank, standard and sample were injected into the chromatographic system and areas for the Flouxatine and Olanzapine the peaks were used for calculating the % assay by using the formulae.

System suitability

- Tailing factor for the peaks due to Flouxatine and Olanzapine in standard solution should not be more than 1.5.
- Theoretical plates for the Flouxatine and Olanzapine peaks in standard solution should not be less than 2000.

Assay calculation

$$\text{Assay \%} = \frac{\text{sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{dilution sample}}{\text{dilution of standard}} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \frac{\text{Avg. wt}}{Lc} \times 100$$

Where:

Avg.wt = average weight of tablets

P= Percentage purity of working standard

Assay Results for Olanzapine =98.2%

Assay Results for Flouxatine =99.1%

ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION**Validation parameters**

- ❖ Specificity
- ❖ Linearity
- ❖ Range
- ❖ Accuracy
- ❖ Precision
 - ❖ Repeatability
 - ❖ Intermediate Precision
- ❖ Detection Limit
- ❖ Quantitation Limit

1. Specificity

The system suitability for specificity was carried out to determine whether there is any interference of any impurities in retention time of analytical peak. The specificity was performed by injecting blank.

2. Linearity**Preparation of stock solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 12.5 mg&8mg of Olanzapine and Flouxatine working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution).

Preparation of Level – I (25ppmof Olanzapine &16ppmof Flouxatine):

0.2ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – II (50ppmof Olanzapine &32ppmof Flouxatine):

0.4ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – III (75ppmof Olanzapine &48ppmof Flouxatine):

0.6ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – IV (100ppmof Olanzapine &64ppmof Flouxatine):

0.8ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – V (125ppmof Olanzapine &80ppmof Flouxatine)

1.0 of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure

Each level was injected into the chromatographic system and peak area was measured. Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and the correlation coefficient was calculated.

Acceptance criteria

- ❖ Correlation coefficient should be not less than 0.999.

3. Range

Based on precision, linearity and accuracy data it can be concluded that the assay method is precise, linear and accurate in the range of 16µg/ml-80µg/ml and 25µg/ml to 125µg/ml of Flouxatine and Olanzapine respectively.

4. Accuracy**Preparation of standard stock solution**

Accurately weigh and transfer 12.5 mg &8 mg of Olanzapine and Flouxatine working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonic ate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine &Flouxatine the above stock solution into a10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent

Preparation of sample solutions**For preparation of 50% solution (with respect to target assay concentration)**

Accurately weigh and transfer 7mg of Hydrochloro thiozide and 4.25mg of Flouxatine working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock Solution).

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine &Flouxatine the above stock

For preparation of 100% solution (with respect to target assay concentration)

Accurately weigh and transfer 13.1mg of Olanzapine and 8.25mg of Flouxatine working standards into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution).

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine & Flouxatine the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For preparation of 150% solution (with respect to target assay concentration)

Accurately weigh and transfer 18.5mg of Olanzapine and 12.2mg of Flouxatine working standards into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution).

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine & Flouxatine the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent

Procedure

The standard solutions of accuracy 50%, 100% and 150% were injected into chromatographic system. Calculate the amount found and amount added for Flouxatine and Olanzapine and calculate the individual % recovery and mean % recovery values.

Acceptance criteria

- ❖ The % recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0%

5. Precision

5.1 Repeatability

Preparation of stock solution

Accurately weigh and transfer 12.5 mg & 8 mg of Olanzapine and Flouxatine working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonic ate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine & Flouxatine the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent

Procedure: The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits..

Acceptance criteria

- ❖ The % RSD for the area of five standard injections results should not be more than 2.

5.2 Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as ruggedness) of the method, precision was performed on different days by using different make column of same dimensions.

Preparation of stock solution

Accurately weigh and transfer 12.5 mg & 8 mg of Olanzapine and Flouxatine working standard into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 7mL of Diluent and sonic ate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

(Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.6ml of Olanzapine & Flouxatine the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent

Procedure

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Acceptance criteria

- ❖ The % RSD for the area of five sample injections results should not be more than 2%.

6. Limit of detection (LOD)

LOD's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

Formula:

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where

σ - Standard deviation (SD)

S - Slope

7. Limit of quantification

LOQ's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

Formula:

$$LOQ = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where

σ - Standard deviation

S - Slope

8. Robustness

As part of the robustness, deliberate change in the flow rate, mobile phase composition was made to evaluate the impact on the method.

- The flow rate was varied at 0.9 ml/min to 1.1ml/min. Standard solution 75ppm of Olanzapine & 48 ppm of Flouxatine was prepared and analysed using the varied flow rates along with method flow rate.
- The Organic composition in the Mobile phase was varied from 55% to 65%.

Standard solution 75 μ g/ml of Olanzapine & 48 μ g/ml of Flouxatine was prepared and analysed using the varied Mobile phase composition along

with the actual mobile phase composition in the method.

Method Development

The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10µg/ml for individual and mixed standards. The

resulting solution was scanned in U.V range from 200-400nm. The overlay spectrum of Flouxatine and Olanzapine was obtained and the isobestic point of Flouxatine and Olanzapine showed absorbance's maxima at 240 nm. The spectrums are shown.

Assay calculation for Flouxatine and Olanzapine

The assay study was performed for the Flouxatine and Olanzapine. Each three injections of sample and standard were injected into chromatographic system. The chromatograms are shown in Figures and results are tabulated.

Chromatogram showing assay of sample injection-1,2

	PeakName	RT	Area	Height	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Flouxatine	2.170	1333112	164078	2114.9	1.7
2	Flouxatine	2.166	1355521	164511	2127.0	1.7
3	Olanzapine	2.757	462181	44873	2931.4	1.7
4	Olanzapine	7.197	465519	41056	2697.1	1.7

S. No	Name of compound	Label claim(mg)	Amount taken(mg)	%purity
1	Flouxatine	8	58.9	99.1
2	Olanzapine	12.5	58.9	98.2

	PeakName	RT	Area	Height	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Flouxatine	2.170	1324213	125075	2115.8	1.7
2	Flouxatine	2.312	1455213	163422	2126.0	1.7
3	Olanzapine	7.280	461281	34873	2921.4	1.7
4	Olanzapine	6.124	564481	31068	6284.1	1.7

Linearity

The linearity study was performed for the concentration of 25 ppm to 150 for Olanzapine and 16ppm to 80ppm for Flouxatine. Each level was injected into chromatographic system. The area of each level was used for calculation of correlation coefficient. The results are tabulated. Calibration graph are shown in Fig.

Chromatograms showing linearity level-1 to level 5

Linearity Results for Flouxatine:

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	16ppm	1027461
2	II	32ppm	1233566
3	III	48ppm	1437030
4	IV	64ppm	1644336
5	V	80ppm	1880590
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Showing calibration graph for Flouxatine

Linearity Results for Olanzapine:

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	25ppm	2201022
2	II	50ppm	2585033
3	III	75ppm	2996553
4	IV	100ppm	3446224
5	V	125ppm	3897922
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Showing calibration graph for Olanzapine

Accuracy

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	765624	4.25	4.30	101.2%	101.4%
100%	1508055	8.25	8.48	101.5%	
150%	2204983	12.2	12.39	101.6%	

Showing accuracy results for Olanzapine

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1726242	7.05	7.1	101.9%	101.7%
100%	3187170	13.1	13.2	101.3%	
150%	4521881	18.5	18.8	101.8%	

Precision

Chromatograms showing precision injections -1 to 5

Showing % RSD results for Flouxatine

Injection	Area
Injection-1	1475698
Injection-2	1461561
Injection-3	1481379
Injection-4	1467049
Injection-5	1472628
Average	1471663
Standard Deviation	7664.08
%RSD	0.52

Table.No.11. Showing %RSD results for Olanzapine

Injection	Area
Injection-1	3045768
Injection-2	3030853
Injection-3	3063519
Injection-4	3065127
Injection-5	3099001
Average	3060854
Standard Deviation	25535.28
%RSD	0.83

Detection limit

LOD's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

Formula:

$$LOD = 3.3 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where

σ - Standard deviation (SD)

S - Slope

Fig.44 Results of LOD

	Name	Retention Time (min)	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)
1	Flouxatine	2.184	1236	142
2	Olanzapine	7.503	1208	162

Results of LOD

Drug name	Baseline noise(μV)	Signal obtained (μV)	S/N ratio
Flouxatine	31	121	2.85
Olanzapine	31	121	4.03

Quantitation limit

LOQ's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

Formula:

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where

σ - Standard deviation

S - Slope

Results of LOQ

CONCLUSION:

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Flouxatine and Olanzapine by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Flouxatine and Olanzapine by using Zodiac sil C18 column (4.6×150mm)5 μ , flow rate was 1ml/min,

mobile phase ratio was (70:30 v/v) methanol: phosphate buffer(KH₂PO₄and K₂HPO₄) phosphate pH 3 (pH was adjusted with orthophosphoricacid),detection wavelength was 240nm.

The instrument used was WATERS HPLC Auto Sampler, Separation module 2695, photo diode array detector

996, Empower-software version-2. The retention times were found to be 2.170 mins and 7.025 mins. The % purity of Flouxatine and Olanzapine was found to be 99.1% and 98.2% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Flouxatine and Olanzapine such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 12294, 1.27 and 10491 and 1.03, the resolution was found to be 8.67. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study of Flouxatine and Olanzapine was found in concentration range of 16µg-80µg and 25µg-125µg and correlation coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.999 and 0.998, % recovery was found to be 101.7% and 102.0%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.8 and 0.5, % RSD for intermediate precision was 1.99 and 1.82 respectively. The precision study was precision, robustness and repeatability. LOD value was 2.17 and 0.0372 and LOQ value was 6.60 and 0.1125 respectively.

Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Flouxatine and Olanzapine in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

REFERENCES:

1. Yuri Kazakevich and Rosario Lobrutto, HPLC for Pharmaceutical Scientists, 1st edition, Wiley Interscience A John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Publication, (2007), PP 15-23.
2. A. Braithwait and F.J. Smith, Chromatographic Methods, 5th edition, Kluwer Academic Publisher, (1996), PP 1-2.
3. Dr. Kealey and P.J Haines, Analytical Chemistry, 1st edition, Bios Publisher, (2002), PP 1-7 Chromatography, (online). URL: <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chromatography>.
4. Meyer V.R. Practical High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, 4th Ed. England, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, (2004), PP 7-8.
5. Andrea Weston and Phyllisr. Brown, HPLC Principle and Practice, 1st edition, Academic press, (1997), PP 24-37.
6. Sahajwalla CG a new drug development, vol 141, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, (2004), PP 421-426.
7. Introduction to Column. (Online), URL: http://amitpatel745.topcities.com/index_files/study/column_care.pdf
8. Detectors used in HPLC (online) URL: http://wiki.answers.com/Q/What_detectors_are_used_in_HPLC
9. Detectors (online), URL: http://hplc.chem.shu.edu/NEW/HPLC_Book/Detectors/det_uvda.html
10. Detectors (online), URL: http://www.dionex.com/enus/webdocs/64842-31644-02_PDA-100.pdf